

The Effect of Co-Curricular Activities on Learners Academic Performance: A Case of Selected Secondary Schools in Lusaka District, Zambia

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Abstract:

Overview: This study investigated the effect of co-curricular activities on learners' academic performance in selected secondary schools in Lusaka District, Zambia. It aimed to explore how participation in activities such as sports, arts, and clubs influences students' academic outcomes.

Body of Knowledge: The study examined the relationship between involvement in these activities and academic achievement, considering factors such as student engagement, time management, and motivation. By analyzing the experiences and perceptions of students, teachers, and school administrators, the study sought to determine whether co-curricular participation enhances or hinders academic performance, offering insights into the broader implications for educational policy and practice in Zambia.

Methods: The study employed a descriptive correlational design to examine the relationship between participation in co-curricular activities and academic performance among secondary school students. The study utilized stratified random sampling to ensure representation from different schools and co-curricular activities. The sample size was 200 respondents, consisting of Officials from DEBS office, Head teachers, Teachers, and Pupils from four selected secondary schools within Lusaka district of Zambia. Questionnaires and academic records were used to collect quantitative data while interviews were used to collect qualitative data from the participants. The study used appropriate statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics using SPSS and Microsoft Excel to analyze the quantitative data whereas qualitative data obtained were analyzed thematically.

Results: The findings showed that co-curricular activities offer a platform for students to apply the theoretical knowledge gained in class to real-world scenarios, enhancing their understanding and retention of academic concepts. Additionally, co-curricular activities contribute to the social and emotional well-being of learners, which is closely linked to academic success. Co-curricular activities are integral to the academic performance of learners as they support the development of critical life skills, reinforce academic learning through practical application, and enhance social and emotional well-being.

Recommendation: The study calls for educational policy and practice, emphasizing the importance of balancing academic and non-academic pursuits to foster well-rounded student development.

Keywords: Academic performance, Co-curricular Activities, Educational Outcomes, Secondary Schools, and Student Engagement.

1. INTRODUCTION

Co-curricular activities have a significant effect on learners' academic performance, serving as a crucial complement to the formal curriculum. These activities, which include sports, arts, clubs, and societies, contribute to students' holistic development by enhancing their social skills, discipline, and time management. Engaging in co-curricular activities often leads to improved academic outcomes as they help in the development of a well-rounded skill set, including leadership and teamwork abilities (UNESCO, 2015). Additionally, such activities can foster a sense of belonging and motivation, which can positively influence a student's commitment to their studies. The structured environment of co-curricular programs can also provide practical experiences that reinforce classroom learning, thereby improving academic performance. Moreover, students who participate in these activities tend to develop better problem-solving skills and a more positive attitude towards learning, which can translate into higher academic achievement. However, it is essential to balance co-curricular involvement with academic responsibilities to ensure that students do not experience burnout or neglect their studies.

Co-curricular activities refer to the various programs and activities that complement the formal academic curriculum in educational institutions (Banda, 2012). These activities, which can include sports, arts, music, drama, clubs, and community service, are designed to enhance the holistic development of students by providing opportunities for them to explore their interests and talents beyond the classroom. Co-curricular activities in secondary schools refer to those activities that complement the academic curriculum and contribute to the holistic development of students. These activities are designed to enhance students' social, emotional, physical, and intellectual growth, going beyond the confines of traditional classroom learning (Musakanya & Chanda, 2024). Co-curricular activities play a crucial role in fostering social skills, teamwork, leadership, and personal responsibility, as they often involve collaboration and active participation. By engaging in these activities, students can develop a well-rounded personality, gain practical experience, and cultivate a sense of belonging and community within the school environment.

Academic performance refers to the extent to which a student, teacher, or institution has achieved their short- or long-term educational goals. Kikwato et al (2023) says that it is typically measured through various means such as grades, test scores, class participation, and the completion of assignments. Academic performance is often used as an indicator of a student's learning progress and overall competency in a particular subject or course. It can also reflect the effectiveness of teaching methods, the quality of educational resources, and the influence of external factors such as family support and socio-economic status. High academic performance is generally associated with a deep understanding of the material, strong problem-solving skills, and the ability to apply knowledge in practical situations, while poor academic performance may indicate a need for additional support or intervention (Chanda, 2024).

Student engagement in co-curricular activities refers to the active involvement of students in non-academic pursuits that complement their formal education. These activities, which can include sports, clubs, arts, community service, and leadership programs, provide students with opportunities to develop skills beyond the classroom. Engagement in co-curricular activities is characterized by students' participation, enthusiasm, and commitment to these extracurricular pursuits (DiFiore, 2023). It fosters a sense of belonging, enhances personal development, and often leads to improved academic performance and social skills. By participating in co-curricular activities, students can explore their interests, build relationships, and gain experiences that contribute to their overall growth and well-being.

Educational outcomes refer to the measurable results and impacts of educational processes on students' knowledge, skills, attitudes, and overall development. These outcomes encompass a range of achievements, including academic performance, personal growth, and social skills. They are often evaluated through various assessments, such as tests, assignments, and observational studies, to determine how effectively educational goals and objectives are being met. Rucker (2023) says that educational outcomes can include improvements in critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and the capacity to apply learned concepts in real-world situations. They also reflect the extent to which educational programs and teaching methods have succeeded in enhancing students' readiness for further education, the workforce, and active citizenship. Ultimately, educational outcomes serve as a key indicator of the success and quality of educational systems and their impact on learners' future prospects.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The impact of co-curricular activities on learners' academic performance remains a subject of considerable debate and investigation within the educational sector. In the context of secondary schools in Lusaka District, Zambia, there is a growing interest in understanding how engagement in activities beyond the classroom, such as sports, clubs, and societies, influences students' academic outcomes. Despite the widespread incorporation of co-curricular programs in school curricula, there is limited empirical evidence to clarify whether these activities enhance or detract from academic performance (Musakanya & Chanda, 2024). This study aimed to address the gap by examining the relationship between participation in co-curricular activities and academic achievement among secondary school students in Lusaka District. The findings might provide valuable insights into how these activities contribute to students' holistic development and their academic success, offering guidance for educators and policymakers in designing balanced educational programs that support both academic and extracurricular growth.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the impact of co-curricular activities on the academic performance of learners in selected secondary schools within Lusaka District, Zambia.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

- To evaluate the impact of participation in co-curricular activities on academic performance of learners in selected secondary schools of Lusaka district, Zambia.
- To identify the relationship between different types of co-curricular activities and educational outcomes in selected secondary schools of Lusaka district, Zambia.

1.5 Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by the Social Learning Theory. This theory was proposed by Albert Bandura, posits that learning occurs through observation, imitation, and modeling within a social context. In the context of co-curricular activities and their impact on academic performance in secondary schools in Lusaka District, Zambia, Social Learning Theory suggests that these activities play a crucial role in shaping students' academic outcomes. When students participate in co-curricular activities such as sports, clubs, and arts, they often model behaviors and attitudes from their peers and mentors, which can enhance their learning experiences. Mulemwa & Chanda (2023) added that these activities provide opportunities for students to observe and practice skills, collaborate with others, and receive feedback, all of which can contribute to their overall academic development. Additionally, the social interactions and positive reinforcement experienced in co-curricular settings can boost students' self-esteem and motivation, leading to improved academic performance. By integrating these activities into the educational framework, secondary schools in Lusaka District can foster a more holistic learning environment that supports both academic and personal growth.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The significance of studying the effect of co-curricular activities on learners' academic performance in selected secondary schools in Lusaka District, Zambia, lies in understanding how these activities contribute to holistic student development and academic achievement. Co-curricular activities, which encompass sports, clubs, and cultural events, play a crucial role in enhancing students' skills, discipline, and time management. By examining their impact on academic performance, this study aims to provide insights into how participation in such activities can complement classroom learning, foster a more engaging educational environment, and potentially improve academic outcomes. Understanding these dynamics is vital for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders to design well-rounded educational programs that balance academic rigor with co-curricular involvement, thereby supporting the overall growth and success of students.

2. METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive correlational design to examine the relationship between participation in co-curricular activities and academic performance among secondary school students. The study utilized stratified random sampling to ensure representation from different schools and co-curricular activities. The study was conducted in 4 secondary schools in Lusaka district of Zambia. The target population was 2000 and sampled 200 respondents which was 10% of the targeted number. The sample consisted 2 Officials from DEBS office, 4 head teachers, 1 representing each selected school, 20 teachers, 5 representing each selected school, and 84 pupils, 21 representing each selected school. The study made use of the questionnaires, and academic

records to collect quantitative data while interviews were used to collect qualitative data from the participants. The quantitative data collected were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) and Microsoft Excel whereas the qualitative data were analyzed thematically. The study upheld research ethical considerations such as voluntary participation of the respondents, confidentiality, honesty, and right of privacy.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Impact of Participation in Co-Curricular Activities on Academic Performance of Learners

3.1.1 Positive Impact of Participation in Co-Curricular Activities on Academic Performance of Learners

According to research findings, participation in co-curricular activities has been increasingly recognized for its positive influence on students' academic performance, primarily through the development of soft skills. These activities, which include sports, arts, debate clubs, and community service, provide a platform for students to hone skills beyond the traditional academic curriculum. Soft skills such as communication, teamwork, leadership, problem-solving, and time management are significantly enhanced through active involvement in these activities (Mupa, 2015). One of the key soft skills developed through co-curricular participation is effective communication. Engaging in debates, public speaking, or collaborative projects requires students to articulate their ideas clearly and confidently. Phiri et al (2023) added that this practice translates into improved verbal and written communication skills in academic settings. Enhanced communication skills enable students to express their understanding more effectively during presentations and written assignments, thereby positively impacting their academic performance (Madoda et al, 2024). Teamwork is another crucial soft skill fostered by co-curricular activities. Many activities involve group work, requiring students to collaborate, share responsibilities, and resolve conflicts. These experiences teach students how to work harmoniously with others, build relationships, and manage interpersonal dynamics. The ability to work well in teams is invaluable in academic settings, where group projects and discussions are common. Students who excel in teamwork often demonstrate better problem-solving skills and achieve higher grades.

Leadership and organizational skills are also significantly developed through co-curricular activities. Students who take on leadership roles in clubs, sports teams, or other groups learn to manage tasks, motivate peers, and make decisions. These skills contribute to a student's ability to handle academic responsibilities more effectively, manage time efficiently, and set goals (Musyoka, 2017). As a result, students who are adept at leadership and organization often exhibit improved academic performance due to their enhanced ability to balance and prioritize various tasks. Problem-solving skills are cultivated through participation in activities that challenge students to think critically and creatively. Whether it's solving complex problems in a science club, strategizing in sports, or addressing community issues in service projects, students learn to approach problems systematically and develop innovative solutions. These problem-solving abilities are directly applicable to academic challenges, helping students approach their

coursework with a more analytical mindset and a greater capacity for overcoming obstacles (Chanda et al, 2023).

Additionally, participation in co-curricular activities is widely recognized for its benefits beyond the academic realm, particularly in fostering enhanced social skills among students. In secondary schools within Lusaka District, the engagement in various co-curricular activities such as sports, debate clubs, drama, and music plays a crucial role in shaping students' social interactions and overall academic performance. One of the significant impacts of co-curricular activities is the development of communication skills. These activities often require students to collaborate, present ideas, and engage in discussions, which can improve their ability to express themselves clearly and effectively (Chitondo et al, 2024). For example, students involved in debate clubs or drama often experience heightened self-confidence and poise, skills that are transferable to classroom interactions and public speaking. This enhanced communication capability contributes positively to their academic performance by facilitating better understanding and articulation of academic content.

Moreover, co-curricular activities offer students opportunities to develop teamwork and leadership skills. Working in teams for sports or group projects requires students to navigate different personalities, manage conflicts, and work towards common goals. Chanda et al (2024)'s study noted that conflict resolution mechanisms in multi-ethnic societies are multifaceted, aiming to address the unique challenges arising from diverse cultural, ethnic, and social backgrounds. These experiences help students learn how to cooperate with others, delegate tasks, and lead effectively, all of which are valuable in both academic settings and future professional environments. This ability to work well with others can lead to improved group dynamics in classroom settings and enhance collaborative learning experiences. Furthermore, participation in co-curricular activities can foster better time management and organizational skills (Chekol, 2021). Balancing academic responsibilities with co-curricular commitments requires students to plan and prioritize their tasks efficiently. This improved time management often translates into better study habits and a more disciplined approach to academics. Students who can effectively juggle multiple responsibilities are likely to perform better academically due to their enhanced organizational skills. Additionally, involvement in co-curricular activities can contribute to improved emotional well-being. Engaging in activities that students are passionate about can serve as a stress-reliever and provide a sense of accomplishment and satisfaction. This positive emotional state can have a ripple effect on academic performance by reducing anxiety and enhancing focus and motivation.

The respondents alluded that participation in co-curricular activities plays a significant role in mitigating stress among students, which in turn positively influences their academic performance. In secondary schools within Lusaka District, engaging in various extracurricular activities such as sports, music, drama, and debate has been observed to provide students with effective stress relief mechanisms. These activities offer a productive outlet for students to channel their energy and emotions, helping them to manage the pressures associated with academic demands (Kabungo, 2017). One of the teachers pointed out that:

“Co-curricular activities often provide a healthy outlet for stress and can contribute to better mental health. This can help students maintain focus and perform better academically”.

Research indicates that students involved in co-curricular activities experience lower levels of stress compared to their peers who are not engaged in such activities. Mutambo (2018) noted that this reduction in stress can be attributed to several factors. To begin with, the structured nature of co-curricular activities helps students develop time management skills, allowing them to balance academic responsibilities with extracurricular commitments more efficiently. The sense of accomplishment and enjoyment derived from these activities also contributes to an improved mood and overall well-being.

Additionally, participation in co-curricular activities fosters a sense of belonging and social support among students. Chanda (2024) noted that the friendships and networks formed through these activities create a supportive environment where students can share their challenges and receive encouragement. This social support is crucial in reducing feelings of isolation and anxiety, which are common stressors in academic settings. Furthermore, the physical and mental engagement required in co-curricular activities serves as a diversion from academic stressors. For instance, sports and physical activities help in the release of endorphins, which are natural mood enhancers. Similarly, involvement in creative activities such as music and drama provides an emotional outlet, reducing feelings of stress and enhancing overall mental health (Din, 2006). The positive impact of stress relief on academic performance is evident as students who manage stress effectively tend to perform better academically. Reduced stress levels contribute to improved concentration, better study habits, and enhanced cognitive functioning. Consequently, students who participate in co-curricular activities often exhibit higher levels of academic achievement and a more positive attitude towards their studies.

The results further revealed that participation in co-curricular activities has been widely recognized for its positive influence on students' academic performance. One of the most notable benefits is the increased motivation it fosters among learners. Engaging in activities outside the traditional classroom setting, such as sports, debate clubs, or arts, can significantly enhance students' enthusiasm towards their academic responsibilities (Chanda, 2023). This heightened motivation often translates into improved focus and a stronger commitment to their studies. In secondary schools within Lusaka District, the integration of co-curricular activities into the educational framework has been shown to create a more dynamic and engaging learning environment. Students who participate in these activities tend to experience a greater sense of accomplishment and self-worth, which can spill over into their academic endeavors. For instance, involvement in team sports can instill discipline and teamwork skills, which are beneficial for collaborative projects and classroom interactions. Similarly, participation in debate or drama clubs can enhance critical thinking and public speaking skills, contributing to more active classroom engagement and better academic performance. Moreover, co-curricular activities offer students a platform to explore and develop their interests and talents. This exploration often leads to a more profound connection to their education, as students see the relevance of their academic subjects in real-world contexts (Eccles & Barber, 1999). The sense of achievement and recognition gained from excelling in co-

curricular activities can boost students' confidence, further fueling their academic motivation. By creating a balanced educational experience that includes both academic and non-academic pursuits, secondary schools in Lusaka District can help foster a more motivated and academically successful student body.

The officials from DEBS office narrated that in selected secondary schools of Lusaka District, students involved in various co-curricular activities, such as sports, music, and debate, have shown marked improvements in their ability to manage time effectively. This improvement is attributed to the structured nature of these activities, which require students to adhere to schedules, balance multiple responsibilities, and set priorities. One of the officials explained that:

“Co-curricular activities often necessitate a well-defined time commitment, pushing students to allocate specific time slots for practice, meetings, or rehearsals. This structured schedule fosters a disciplined approach to time management”.

Oliva (2015) noted that students learn to balance their academic responsibilities with their co-curricular commitments, which promotes the development of essential organizational skills. By regularly engaging in such activities, students become adept at setting clear goals, planning their study sessions, and managing deadlines more efficiently.

Furthermore, the skills acquired from managing co-curricular commitments often translate into improved academic performance. Students who are proficient in managing their time effectively can dedicate more focused and productive periods to their studies, leading to better preparation for exams and assignments. The discipline and organization required for balancing co-curricular activities with academic work contribute to a more structured approach to studying and completing school-related tasks (Chanda et al, 2023). In Lusaka District, evidence suggests that students who actively participate in co-curricular activities tend to demonstrate enhanced academic performance compared to their peers who are less engaged in such activities. This correlation underscores the value of co-curricular involvement not only for its direct benefits but also for its role in fostering skills that are crucial for academic success. Adams (2021) added that the improved time management skills gained through co-curricular participation are a significant positive impact that contributes to the academic achievement of students in secondary schools.

Figure1: Positive Impact of Participation in Co-Curricular Activities on Academic Performance of Learners

3.1.2 Negative Impact of Participation in Co-Curricular Activities on Academic Performance of Learners

Findings on the negative impact of participation in co-curricular activities on academic performance revealed that Prioritization of Activities over Academics was at 25%, Risk of Injury at 20%, Lack of Focus at 15%, Fatigue and Physical Exhaustion at 15%, Social Pressure and Peer Influence at 15%, and Sleep Patterns at 10%.

According to the results, participation in co-curricular activities in selected secondary schools of Lusaka district can lead to the prioritization of these activities over academics, which negatively impacts students' academic performance. When students become highly engaged in sports, arts, or other extracurricular pursuits, they may allocate more time and energy to these activities at the expense of their academic responsibilities. This shift in focus can result in reduced study time, missed assignments, and a general decline in academic commitment (Dewi et al, 2021). The competitive nature of some co-curricular activities, such as sports, often requires rigorous training schedules and participation in events that may conflict with study time. Students who are highly invested in these activities may struggle to balance their academic workload with the demands of their co-curricular commitments. As a result, their academic performance may suffer due to insufficient preparation for exams, incomplete coursework, and decreased classroom engagement. Moreover, the social rewards and recognition associated with success in co-curricular activities

can lead students to prioritize these activities over their academic goals (Eccles & Gootman, 2002). The immediate gratification of winning a competition or being celebrated for artistic talents might overshadow the long-term benefits of academic achievement. This prioritization can be particularly pronounced in cases where students perceive co-curricular success as a more attainable or desirable goal compared to academic excellence.

The results also showed that participation in co-curricular activities, while beneficial for holistic student development, carries the inherent risk of injury, which can negatively impact academic performance. In selected secondary schools of Lusaka District, students involved in physical activities such as sports are particularly susceptible to injuries. These injuries can range from minor sprains to more severe conditions that may require extended recovery periods. One of the head teachers explained that:

“When students are injured, their ability to attend classes, concentrate, and complete assignments is compromised. This can lead to missed lessons, incomplete coursework, and reduced engagement in academic activities”.

Moreover, the time spent recovering from injuries can disrupt a student's academic routine, leading to a decline in performance. For instance, a student who sustains a sports-related injury may need to take time off from school, leading to gaps in learning and a backlog of work that can be overwhelming to catch up on. In severe cases, students may also experience a decline in motivation due to their inability to participate fully in both academic and co-curricular activities, further exacerbating the negative impact on their academic achievements. In addition to the physical effects, the psychological impact of injuries should not be overlooked. Students who are passionate about their co-curricular pursuits may experience frustration, anxiety, or depression when sidelined by an injury. This emotional distress can spill over into their academic life, leading to a lack of focus and decreased academic performance (Cadwallader et al, 2002). The pressure to balance recovery with academic responsibilities can also add to their stress, creating a challenging environment for academic success.

The findings further noted that participation in co-curricular activities can inadvertently lead to distraction and a lack of focus, negatively impacting academic performance. Students often face challenges in managing their time effectively when they engage in various activities beyond the classroom (Mboози et al, 2024). Balancing academic responsibilities with the demands of sports, arts, or club activities can lead to divided attention, where students struggle to dedicate sufficient time and mental energy to their studies. This lack of focus is further exacerbated when students prioritize their involvement in co-curricular activities over academics. The excitement and social interactions that come with these activities may cause students to lose sight of their academic goals, leading to procrastination and incomplete assignments (MoE, 2012). Over time, this shift in focus can result in declining academic performance, as students may find it difficult to concentrate during lessons or lack the motivation to study. Moreover, the physical and mental exhaustion from participation in co-curricular activities can contribute to reduced cognitive function, making it

harder for students to absorb and retain information. This distraction, coupled with the lack of sufficient rest, can diminish a student's ability to perform well in exams and other academic assessments. In some cases, the overemphasis on co-curricular success may lead to a situation where students become disengaged from their academic pursuit's altogether, seeing them as secondary to their achievements in other areas.

Teachers observed that participation in co-curricular activities, while beneficial in many aspects, can lead to significant fatigue and physical exhaustion, which negatively impacts students' academic performance. In selected secondary schools of Lusaka district, students who are heavily involved in sports, arts, or other extracurricular pursuits often find themselves physically drained, especially when these activities are scheduled alongside demanding academic responsibilities. The physical strain from intense practices, competitions, or performances can lead to reduced energy levels, making it difficult for students to concentrate during classes or dedicate sufficient time to their studies (Blum, 1990). This exhaustion often results in decreased cognitive function, leading to slower information processing and poorer retention of academic material. Additionally, the need to balance both academics and extracurricular commitments can lead to insufficient rest, exacerbating the effects of fatigue and causing a decline in overall academic performance. In some cases, the pressure to excel in both areas may overwhelm students, leading to burnout, which further diminishes their academic achievements.

On the other hand, officials from DEBS office stated that participation in co-curricular activities can expose students to social pressure and peer influence, which may negatively impact their academic performance. Chanda (2023) supported this finding by stating that when students engage in these activities, they often find themselves in social groups where the norms and values may prioritize success in the activity over academic achievement. For instance, a student involved in a sports team may feel pressured by teammates to prioritize practice sessions, games, or social events related to the sport over studying or completing assignments. Chakulimba (2007) says that this peer pressure can lead to a shift in focus, where the student's dedication to academics diminishes in favor of meeting the expectations of their peers within the co-curricular environment. Moreover, the desire to fit in or be accepted by peers involved in co-curricular activities can lead to behaviors that are detrimental to academic success. Students may skip classes, procrastinate on assignments, or even neglect studying altogether in order to participate in or socialize around the co-curricular activity. This influence can be particularly strong in activities that demand a significant time commitment or that are highly competitive, where the pressure to perform well in the activity can overshadow the importance of maintaining good academic standing. Additionally, peer influence can also manifest in the adoption of attitudes that devalue academic achievements. In some social circles within co-curricular activities, academic success may not be regarded as important or may even be viewed as less desirable compared to excelling in the activity itself. This cultural shift can lead students to prioritize short-term social rewards, such as popularity or recognition in the co-curricular space, over long-term academic goals. Consequently, Mwashingwele (2015) noted that the pressure to conform to these peer-driven expectations can result in lower grades, reduced

academic engagement, and ultimately, a negative impact on the student's overall academic performance.

Respondents also noted that participation in co-curricular activities can significantly disrupt students' sleep patterns, leading to negative consequences on their academic performance. The demands of these activities often extend beyond regular school hours, requiring students to devote additional time to practice, preparation, or competitions. This increased time commitment can result in late nights, reduced sleep, and irregular sleep schedules. As students try to balance their academic responsibilities with their involvement in co-curricular activities, they may find themselves sacrificing sleep to meet the demands of both (Palmieri, 2017). One of the pupils revealed that:

“Co-curricular activities often extend into the evening, which can interfere with their' sleep schedules. Lack of adequate sleep is directly linked to decreased cognitive function and poorer academic performance”.

The impact on sleep patterns is particularly concerning because adequate sleep is crucial for cognitive function, memory consolidation, and overall well-being. When students do not get enough sleep, they may experience difficulties in concentrating, retaining information, and performing well in class. Chronic sleep deprivation can also lead to mood disturbances, increased stress levels, and a decrease in motivation, further exacerbating the challenges students face in their academic pursuits (Varja, 2018). The negative impact on sleep patterns due to participation in co-curricular activities highlights the need for a balanced approach to student involvement, ensuring that the benefits of these activities do not come at the expense of their academic success and overall health.

Figure2: Negative Impact of Participation in Co-Curricular Activities on Academic Performance of Learners

3.2. The Relationship between Different Types of Co-Curricular Activities and Educational Outcomes

According to study results, exploring the relationship between different types of co-curricular activities and educational outcomes can provide valuable insights into how these activities influence students' academic performance, personal development, and overall school experience. The findings showed that co-curricular activities play a significant role in the holistic development of students, particularly in the context of secondary schools in Lusaka District. These activities, which range from sports and arts to academic clubs and community service, contribute to academic enrichment by providing students with opportunities to apply classroom knowledge in real-world contexts. For instance, participation in debate clubs and science fairs enhances critical thinking, public speaking, and problem-solving skills, which are directly linked to academic success (Chanda, 2024). These activities allow students to explore and deepen their understanding of academic subjects, thereby reinforcing and expanding their knowledge base. Furthermore, involvement in co-curricular activities fosters a sense of discipline, time management, and

Received: 22 July 2024

Revised: 11 August 2024

Accepted: 17 August 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13335567>

teamwork among students. These skills are essential for academic success as they help students to balance their academic responsibilities with extracurricular engagements. For example, students who participate in sports learn the importance of discipline and teamwork, which can translate into better focus and collaboration in academic settings. The structured environment of co-curricular activities also encourages students to set goals and work towards achieving them, a mindset that is beneficial for academic achievement (Wiranto & Slameto, 2021).

The relationship between different types of co-curricular activities and educational outcomes is multifaceted. Academic clubs and societies, such as mathematics or literature clubs, are directly linked to improved academic performance in related subjects. These activities provide students with additional learning opportunities outside the classroom, allowing them to delve deeper into specific academic interests (Chanda, 2023). On the other hand, activities like music, drama, and sports contribute to the development of soft skills such as creativity, leadership, and emotional intelligence, which are equally important for overall educational outcomes. In the context of Lusaka District, the impact of co-curricular activities on educational outcomes is influenced by several factors, including the availability of resources, the level of student engagement, and the support from educators and parents. Schools that actively promote and integrate co-curricular activities into their curriculum tend to see higher levels of student engagement and academic achievement. This suggests that co-curricular activities are not merely supplementary but integral to the educational process, providing students with a well-rounded education that prepares them for future challenges (Musakanya & Chanda, 2024).

The study also found that sports and physical activities play a significant role in shaping the educational outcomes of students. These activities contribute to the holistic development of students by promoting not only physical fitness but also enhancing cognitive abilities, social skills, and emotional well-being. Regular participation in sports has been linked to improved academic performance, as physical exercise stimulates brain function, increases concentration, and enhances memory (Ngwaru, 2017). Additionally, sports provide students with essential life skills such as teamwork, discipline, time management, and leadership, which are crucial for success both in and out of the classroom. Furthermore, sports and physical activities foster a sense of belonging and school spirit, which can positively impact students' motivation and engagement in academic pursuits. The camaraderie and support systems built through team sports can lead to a more positive school experience, reducing absenteeism and dropout rates. Chanda (2023) defines a drop out as a pupil who was enrolled in the beginning of the school year and has left before the end of the school year, and was not enrolled elsewhere. However, the relationship between sports participation and educational outcomes is complex and can vary depending on factors such as the intensity of involvement, the balance between academics and extracurricular commitments, and the level of support provided by the school and parents. In some cases, excessive focus on sports may lead to challenges such as reduced study time and increased physical exhaustion, which can negatively affect academic performance (Rachel, 2015). Therefore, it is crucial for schools in Lusaka District to strike a balance between encouraging sports participation and ensuring that students maintain their academic responsibilities. Schools that successfully integrate sports into

the educational framework often see students who are more well-rounded, resilient, and better prepared for future challenges.

Officials from DEBS office alluded that creative arts, encompassing activities such as visual arts, music, theater, and dance, play a significant role in shaping educational outcomes through co-curricular involvement. One official noted that:

“Creative arts activities are not merely supplementary but integral to fostering a well-rounded educational experience in the sense that participation in creative arts can have profound effects on students’ cognitive, emotional, and social development, contributing to their overall academic performance and personal growth”.

Engaging in creative arts enhances cognitive abilities by stimulating various mental processes. For example, learning to play a musical instrument or participating in theater requires complex cognitive skills such as memory, attention, and problem-solving. Research indicates that students involved in these activities often exhibit improved academic performance, particularly in subjects that require creative thinking and problem-solving skills. The cognitive benefits of creative arts are attributed to their ability to foster critical thinking and innovative problem-solving, which are transferable to academic tasks (Ngwaru & Oluga, 2015). Creative arts provide a valuable outlet for emotional expression and can help students manage stress and anxiety. Art and music therapy are well-documented for their effectiveness in improving emotional health, which in turn can positively impact academic performance. Students who participate in creative arts often experience increased self-esteem and confidence, which can translate into a more positive attitude toward their studies and school environment. Additionally, the collaborative nature of many creative activities fosters a sense of community and belonging, which further supports emotional well-being.

Participation in creative arts often involves collaboration and teamwork, which are crucial for developing social skills. Activities such as drama productions, group art projects, and musical ensembles require students to work together, communicate effectively, and understand diverse perspectives. These social interactions can enhance interpersonal skills, build leadership qualities, and improve students’ ability to work within a group setting. The social competencies gained through creative arts can enhance students’ experiences in academic group projects and extracurricular activities, leading to improved educational outcomes. Creative arts can also complement and enhance academic learning (Eccles & Gootman, 2002). For instance, integrating visual arts into science or history lessons can provide students with a deeper understanding of the subject matter and make learning more engaging. The skills developed through creative arts, such as attention to detail and creative problem-solving, can improve performance in other academic areas. Additionally, the ability to express ideas creatively can lead to more effective communication and presentation skills, which are valuable across all subjects.

Furthermore, respondents observed that participation in co-curricular activities often plays a crucial role in the development of leadership skills among students. Activities such as student government, debate clubs, and sports teams provide opportunities for students to take on leadership roles, manage projects, and guide their peers. These experiences can enhance students’ ability to lead, make decisions, and work collaboratively (Chanda et al, 2024). The development of

leadership skills through such activities can translate into improved academic performance, as students learn to manage their time effectively, set goals, and handle responsibilities with greater competence. Community service is another significant aspect of co-curricular activities that impacts educational outcomes. Engaging in community service allows students to apply their academic knowledge in real-world settings, fostering a sense of responsibility and empathy. Activities such as volunteering at local organizations, participating in environmental clean-ups, or organizing charity events provide practical experiences that complement classroom learning. The skills gained through community service such as teamwork, problem-solving, and communication can enhance students' overall academic performance and personal growth.

Head teachers explained that the relationship between leadership and community service within co-curricular activities and educational outcomes is multifaceted. On one hand, leadership roles in co-curricular activities can promote critical thinking, organizational skills, and resilience, which are beneficial for academic success. On the other hand, community service can reinforce academic learning by connecting students with practical applications of their studies, thereby increasing motivation and engagement in their education (Barber et al, 2001). While leadership and community service activities offer numerous benefits, it is essential to balance these commitments with academic responsibilities. Over-involvement in co-curricular activities can lead to challenges such as time management issues, increased stress, and potential distractions from academic work. Therefore, students and educators must work together to ensure that participation in co-curricular activities enhances rather than detracts from academic performance.

Additionally, social and cultural clubs within schools represent a distinctive category of co-curricular activities that have a unique impact on educational outcomes. These clubs, which include drama societies, music ensembles, cultural groups, and social advocacy clubs, offer students opportunities to engage in activities that are both personally enriching and educationally beneficial. One of the teachers noted that:

“Participation in social and cultural clubs often fosters a range of skills that are not always emphasized within the traditional academic curriculum. For instance, involvement in drama or music clubs enhances students' creative expression, public speaking abilities, and teamwork skills”.

These clubs provide a platform for students to explore their interests and talents in a supportive environment, which can lead to increased self-confidence and motivation. The skills developed through these activities are transferable to academic settings, potentially improving students' performance by enhancing their ability to communicate effectively and work collaboratively. Cultural clubs, on the other hand, offer students opportunities to learn about and engage with diverse cultural practices and traditions. This exposure can lead to a broader perspective on global issues and foster an appreciation for cultural diversity. Chitondo & Chanda (2023) narrates that diversity is about what makes each of us unique and includes our backgrounds, personality, life experiences and beliefs, all of the things that make us who we are. Such experiences contribute to students' social and emotional development, helping them become more empathetic and open-minded individuals. The ability to understand and navigate diverse cultural contexts is a valuable

skill that can enhance students' academic performance, particularly in subjects that require critical thinking and analysis (Chanda & Madoda, 2024).

Moreover, social and cultural clubs can play a significant role in improving students' social skills and emotional well-being. Through active participation in these clubs, students often form strong peer relationships, develop leadership skills, and learn to manage responsibilities. These social interactions and experiences can reduce feelings of isolation and increase students' engagement with their academic work (Dupri et al, 2019). When students feel connected to their school community and have a sense of belonging, they are more likely to be motivated and perform better academically. However, it is essential to acknowledge that the impact of social and cultural clubs on educational outcomes is not universally positive. For some students, the time and energy invested in these activities can lead to a potential imbalance with academic responsibilities. Excessive involvement in co-curricular activities might result in time constraints that affect students' ability to complete their academic assignments and prepare for exams, potentially leading to decreased academic performance. It is crucial for students to strike a balance between their co-curricular engagements and academic commitments to ensure that their overall educational experience remains positive.

The study also revealed that technology and innovation have significantly influenced the landscape of co-curricular activities, impacting educational outcomes in various ways. With the integration of technology, traditional co-curricular activities, such as sports, music, and debate, have evolved to include digital platforms and tools, enhancing both engagement and effectiveness. For instance, online platforms and software applications have revolutionized how students participate in activities like robotics clubs, coding competitions, and virtual arts exhibitions (Chanda & Phiri, 2024). This digital shift enables a broader reach and inclusivity, allowing students from diverse backgrounds to participate in global events and competitions. Furthermore, the use of technology in these activities fosters critical skills such as problem-solving, teamwork, and digital literacy, which are crucial in the modern educational environment. Innovation in co-curricular activities also introduces new forms of learning experiences, such as gamified learning platforms and interactive simulations, which can make learning more engaging and effective (Pascal, 2017). Chanda et al (2024) added that these advancements help bridge gaps between theoretical knowledge and practical application, thereby improving overall educational outcomes. However, it is important to balance technology use with traditional methods to ensure that students benefit from a well-rounded experience. The effective integration of technology and innovation in co-curricular activities not only enhances students' skills and knowledge but also prepares them for the demands of the 21st-century workforce (Nicholas, 2015).

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study on the effect of co-curricular activities on learners' academic performance in selected secondary schools in Lusaka District, Zambia, reveals a nuanced impact. While co-curricular activities can significantly enhance students' social skills, teamwork, and overall personal development, they also present potential challenges. Issues such as prioritization of

activities over academics, risk of injury, distraction, and fatigue can negatively affect academic performance. The relationship between different types of co-curricular activities and educational outcomes underscores the importance of balanced involvement. Schools should strive to integrate co-curricular programs in a manner that complements academic pursuits, ensuring that students benefit from the holistic development opportunities while maintaining strong academic performance.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are actions that should be taken on the basis of the findings of this study;

1. **Balanced Scheduling and Time Management:**

- Schools should develop and implement balanced schedules that allocate sufficient time for both co-curricular activities and academic work. This can include structured time slots for co-curricular activities to avoid conflicts with academic periods.

2. **Monitoring and Evaluation of Co-Curricular Programs:**

- The Ministry of Education through DEBS offices should establish a system to regularly monitor and evaluate the impact of co-curricular activities on students' academic performance. This can help identify which activities contribute positively or negatively and make necessary adjustments.

3. **Support Systems for Students:**

- Schools should provide support systems to help students manage their participation in co-curricular activities while maintaining academic performance. This can include academic counseling, mentorship programs, and tutoring services.

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Received: 22 July 2024

Revised: 11 August 2024

Accepted: 17 August 2024

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